

A theoretical overview on the role of organizational citizenship behaviors in the promotion of innovation

Une vue théorique sur le rôle des comportements de citoyenneté organisationnelle dans la promotion de l'innovation

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Abstract

The objective of this paper is to emphasize the importance of organizational citizenship behaviors (OCBs) in promoting innovation within organizations. Indeed, thanks to innovation, these organizations will be able to improve their performance and competitiveness. In order to deal with this important topic, we first reviewed the literature to identify the key definitions of OCBs. Then, we drew the most important dimensions of OCB. Moreover, we were able to identify the major outputs and impacts of OCBs. After that, we addressed innovation within organizations by presenting general definitions of this concept and its process' main phases.

Following these definitions, our research focused on identifying the main links and impacts of organizational citizenship behaviors on innovation. This allowed us to propose a model based on the analysis made by the main authors of these concepts. The model that we have proposed in this article can therefore be used in future studies related to our research.

It is important to emphasize that this article aims to raise managers' awareness of the major importance of OCBs on the improvement of innovation within their structures, thus allowing them to achieve gains in terms of performance as well as a better control of internal processes.

Keywords: Organizational Citizenship Behaviors (OCB), Innovation, OCB dimensions, OCB outputs, employees' behaviors, organizational competitiveness.

Résumé

L'objectif de cet article est d'étudier l'importance des comportements de citoyenneté organisationnelle (OCBs) dans la promotion de l'innovation au sein des organisations. Grâce à l'innovation, ces organisations seront capables d'améliorer leurs performances et compétitivité. Afin de traiter ce sujet, nous avons d'abord identifié les principales définitions des OCBs. Ensuite, nous avons défini les dimensions les plus importantes des OCBs. Puis, nous avons identifié les outputs et impacts majeurs des OCBs. Egalement, nous avons abordé l'innovation au sein des organisations en présentant des définitions générales de ce concept et ses principales phases.

Suite à ces définitions, notre recherche a porté sur l'identification des principaux liens et impacts des comportements de citoyenneté organisationnelle sur l'innovation. Ceci nous a permis de proposer un modèle basé sur l'analyse faite par les principaux auteurs de ces concepts. Le modèle que nous avons proposé dans cet article pourra donc être utilisé dans de futures études liées à notre recherche.

Il est important de souligner que cet article vise à sensibiliser les managers à l'importance majeure des OCBs sur l'amélioration de l'innovation au sein de leurs structures, leur permettant ainsi de réaliser des gains en termes de performance ainsi qu'une meilleure maîtrise des processus internes.

Mots clés: Comportements de Citoyenneté Organisationnelle (OCB), Innovation, outputs des OCB, comportements des employés, dimensions des OCB, compétitivité organisationnelle.

Introduction

Innovation is considered as a major lever for the development, competitiveness and sustainability of organizations. As a result, organizations are required to ensure the sustainability and consistency of their innovation processes. Indeed, according to the literature, the organizational citizenship behaviors of managers and employees are a major facilitator of innovation.

For Purvanova et al., 2006, employees can change their perceptions of work through transformational behaviors of leaders, which leads to an improved citizenship performance of these employees. According to Podsakoff and MacKenzie (1997), organizations can improve their ability to adapt to environmental changes through the adoption of organizational citizenship behaviors. Indeed, the success of organizations depends on the degree to which employees adopt OCBs (Neihoff & Yen, 2004).

The OCBs allow building a very important relationship and cooperation between employees, allowing them to contribute with their knowledge and promote innovation (Hsu & Lin, 2008). Different empirical studies show a strong correlation between OCB and organizational performance (Yu & Song, 2014). In fact, this correlation has been verified by Karambayya (1990) and WU Zhiming (2005).

Thus, OCB lets employees develop a willingness to contribute and produce beyond the thresholds required by the employer (Schnake & Dumler, 2003; Feather & Rauter, 2004), allowing for a very positive impact on the psychology of organizational members.

Also, the OCB permits the establishment of a strong cooperation and sportsmanship between the members of the organization, allowing them to share their knowledge (Hsu & Lin, 2008). In this sense, Nemeth (2007) states that these behaviors enhance creative thinking, as a small number of members are able to achieve a very high level of innovation. Thus, Wen-cong (2010) asserts that altruism and self-learning behaviors encourage effective communication channels and fluidity of innovation within the organization.

Therefore, our problematic is articulated as follows: what is the role of organizational citizenship behaviors in promoting innovation? In order to better this relationship, we will first present the different definitions of OCBs. Secondly, we will review the most important dimensions of OCB, including altruism, civic virtue, conscientiousness, courtesy and sportsmanship. Thirdly, we will discuss the outputs of OCBs and their influence in organizations. Then, we will introduce the concept of innovation in organizations. Finally, we

will study the relationship between organizational citizenship behaviors and innovation in organizations, proposing a theoretical model in this sense (figure 1, page 12).

1- Definitions of OCB

Organ is considered as the founding father of the concept of OCB "organizational citizenship behaviors" (Bateman & Organ, 1983; Organ, 1988; Smith et al., 1983). Through this notion, Organ describes the set of specific behaviors that are not part of the employee's job description or the terms of his or her contract with the employer. This is said, the non-adoption of these behaviors by the employees does not inflict any penalty.

For more than three decades, research on OCB has intensified and has led to the emergence of various branches and interpretations of this concept (Borman & Motowidlo, 1997; Podsakoff et al., 2000; Joireman et al., 2006; Bukhari, 2009).

According to Luthans (2005), OCB is the set of behaviors that result from complete freedom of choice, not implicitly or explicitly influenced by a third party. These citizen behaviors are also considered extra efforts beyond the responsibilities required within the organization (Lam et al., 2009). They do indeed fit into a "voluntary" framework to explain that they do not carry a regulatory format of work (İşbaşı, 2000). Mutual aid, helpfulness, and loyalty are as well considered forms of OCB (Podsakoff et al., 2000). In addition, affective commitment to the organization is considered an important indicator for understanding OCB (Lepine et al., 2002; Paillé, 2006; Podsakoff et al., 2000).

In the university context, for example, faculty members' OCB is reflected through their supportive and cooperative acts toward their colleagues and students. It is also important to note that in the context of OCB, professors have a vision of transparency and fairness in procedures (Chidir et al., 2020; Hutagalung et al., 2020; Kusumaningsih et al., 2020; Maesaroh et al., 2020).

2- Dimensions of OCB

As a result of the research conducted by Organ that generated the definition of OCB, Graham (1989) defined four main dimensions of OCB namely: loyalty, individual initiative, personal industry and interpersonal help. According to Moorman (1995), loyalty is the fact that the employee shares a very positive opinion of his or her home organization with external parties. Individual initiative, on the other hand, consists in the fact that an employee can communicate positive messages that stimulate teamwork and the productivity of the organization. According to Graham (1995), personal industry corresponds to the employee's willingness to surpass the

work requirements set by his or her hierarchy. While interpersonal comfort refers to the moment when the employee volunteers to provide help and support to his colleagues. According to research conducted by Paine and Organ (2000), culture is considered an important factor in stimulating employees to engage in OCBs. However, the literature does not fully cover this cultural aspect and its impact on OCB (Becton & Field, 2009).

Workplace integration (Ahmed, Rasheed, & Jehanzeb, 2012), human resource performance (Mukhtav et al., 2012), transformational leadership (Vega-Vázquez et al., 2012), self-efficacy (Dominguez et al., 2013), and cultural background (Paine & Organ, 2000) have also been shown to be important factors for OCB. OCBs are indeed an effective time-saving tool for managers to be able to channel all efforts into exploiting the various opportunities that may arise (Turnipseed & Rassuli, 2005).

In order to increase OCB among employees, various research studies demonstrate the need for the organization to provide organizational justice, job satisfaction and support as well as trust to managers (e.g., Ackfeldt & Coote, 2000; Farh et al., 1990; Moorman, 1991; Organ and Lingl, 1995; Puffer, 1987; Van Dyne et al., 1994; Williams & Anderson, 1991). Indeed, Koys (2001) demonstrated that job satisfaction and organizational commitment can be considered antecedents of OCB. While some authors (George, 1991; Organ & Ryan, 1995; Williams & Anderson, 1991) have considered in previous works that personality traits, attitudes, work climate and the different nature of employees' tasks are also antecedents of OCB. Also, the employee self-report component remains relative to the dimensions of OCB (Blakely et al. 1996). However, the most important dimensions of OCB have been introduced through Organ's five-dimensional model (1990), which we will present below.

2.1- Altruism

Among the main components of the OCB, we can distinguish altruism, which consists in the voluntary character of the employee to cooperate with his colleagues, as well as compliance, which treats the good intention of the employee to respect the internal regulation of the organization (Organ and Ryan, 1995; Williams and Anderson, 1991). Indeed, altruism is considered to be the set of behaviors of employees consisting of providing help and support to their colleagues in the case of difficulties encountered or even during the integration period for new recruits (Organ and Ryan, 1995; Allison et al., 2001).

Altruism is therefore related to the sacrifice made by employees towards the organization. It consists of going beyond the requirements of the job description by helping to support the

employees in their actions. This being said, the interest is to offer support to the individuals with whom a contact is established within the organization. Altruism is therefore a very important antecedent of OCB. The behaviors contained in this dimension are reflected, for example, in the support given by employees to their colleagues who may have a heavy workload, who may have been absent or who may have recently joined their organization. This consists of providing help to employees under specific conditions (Redman & Snape, 2005).

To this end, altruism is a way to make the work dynamic more efficient, in the sense that an employee can convert "down time" to assist colleagues in more urgent situations to ensure the production of their work (Redman & Snape, 2005).

2.2- Civic vertue

According to Organ (1988), civic virtues correspond to the commitment and assiduity of the employee in participating in meetings, events and demonstrations, in a regular and voluntary manner. They consist in the fact that the employee participates in a constructive way in the political life of the organization and offers support to his or her administrative functions (Deluga, 1998). This being said, the employee has a responsibility in the process of participation in the decision-making of his or her organization, among other things, through participation in the various meetings and support for the conduct of organizational change. Graham (1991) mentioned that the employee is required to be a responsible citizen in his or her organization. This dimension of civic virtue is considered to be a factor indicating the level of attachment of the employee to his organization (Podsakoff et al., 2000). It is about ensuring active and sustained participation in the organization's discussions, events and meetings. This allows the employee to be an active player in organizational changes, but also to share information with colleagues (Karaman and Aylan, 2012).

Organizational participation is another name for civic virtue, in the sense that employees are taken into account through a participatory approach in decision making. It is also about ensuring reflections on the organization's structuring subjects (Atalay, 2005).

Some researchers claim that civic virtue is also a vector for reducing customer complaints, as it contributes to improving the quality of organizational performance (Walz & Niehoff, 1996). This being said, employees are stakeholders in ensuring the proper functioning of the organization, hence the fact that civic virtue is an essential aspect for the OCB.

2.3- Conscientiousness

According to Organ (1988), conscientiousness can be expressed by going beyond the requirements formulated by the organization. This may take, for example, the form of voluntary actions, or working overtime. Benevolent behaviors result in exceeding commonly accepted work rules, performance, and attendance (Redman & Snape, 2005). Thus, employees feel a deep attachment and sense of belonging to their organization, which leads to an intrinsic respect for the organization's regulations and procedures.

For Lépine et al (2000), conscientiousness is a key means of performance foresight in organizational decision making, it is also a means of risk management against the advent of the unexpected. In addition, according to Erşahan (2011), conscientiousness is a behavior resulting in optimal and efficient management of working time, beyond the requirements required in the work, in accordance with the regulations in force. In this sense, conscientiousness is in line with the behaviors of punctuality, regularity and commitment. Conscientiousness has a strong relationship with the five dimensions of the OCB (Konovsky & Organ, 1996), and is particularly related to civic virtue and compliance.

According to Organ and Konovsky (1996), conscientiousness is strongly correlated with all aspects of the OCB. It contributes to the improvement of productivity and efficiency of managers in their missions. According to MacKenzie et al. (2001), this improvement can be explained by the commitment of benevolent employees in reducing team conflicts. In addition, Barrick & Mount (1991) state that caring employees are much more effective and efficient than the rest of the employees who are less caring.

In addition, according to Lyubomirsky et al., (2005), conscientiousness provides strategic and targeted guidance and prediction of desired behaviors within the organization. As such, conscientiousness is a source of assurance of high values in any structure.

Conscientiousness also serves to identify high-performing, diligent, responsible and organized individuals. As a result, Morgeson et al., (2005) assert that benevolent individuals require less monitoring, in the sense that they comply with the law and work regulations and ensure that their missions are fulfilled. In addition, because of the competence, diligence and responsibility of these individuals, they are very thorough in their work and are more likely to take the right initiatives to solve organizational problems (Witt et al., 2002).

2.4- Courtesy

In any organization, the art of communication is a key success factor. In this sense, courtesy is defined according to Samancı (2006) as a grouping of positive behaviors from assignments and decisions of employees in the course of their work, so this requires perfect communication with the organization. While Çavuş & Develi (2017) define it as the set of positive behaviors emanating from individuals having exchanges in the context of their work.

Within the organization, courtesy can be manifested by employees turning to their colleagues in case of difficulties encountered in the work. Courtesy also has a preventive dimension in the sense that it includes behaviors whose purpose is to anticipate problems and take the necessary measures to minimize possible negative impacts in the future (Organ, 1988). This being said, these behaviors help to prevent any possibility of interpersonal conflicts between employees, through mutual respect, politeness and civil behavior (Organ, 1990a, b, 1997).

In this sense, courteous co-workers work hard to avoid any potential problems or conflicts that may arise from their colleagues (Podsakoff and MacKenzie, 1997).

Indeed, research has shown that courteous co-workers rarely encounter workgroup conflict. As a result, managers become more efficient and productive in their work (Podsakoff et al., 2000). Therefore, employees make efforts to make the work tasks of their colleagues easier and lighter (Tambe, 2014).

2.5- Sportsmanship

According to Organ (1988), sportsmanship is the ability of an employee to cope with work difficulties without expressly stating them. He also defined this concept as an ability to tolerate unavoidable annoyances within the organization. P. M. Podsakoff et al. (1997) pointed out that sportsmanship is an effective solution against turnover in the organization, as it actively participates in improving the overall work climate. Mohammad et al. (2011) qualified that sportsmanship is the ability of the employee to overcome difficulties and challenges of work even through specific circumstances. That is, he or she is led to overcome and accept certain situations without prioritizing personal interests or complaining.

This dimension of sportsmanship helps to create a climate of efficiency within the organization and contributes to avoid any origin of bad behavior that could emanate from the employees.

3- OCB outputs

A significant body of research has demonstrated the strong impact of OCBs on organizational efficiency and therefore organizational productivity (MacKenzie, Podsakoff & Ahearne, 1998). As a result, employees who engage in organizational citizenship behaviors have high potential for growth within the organization and therefore do not consider changing jobs (Hui, Lam & Law, 2000).

According to Bolino et al., 2002, organizational citizenship behaviors actively contribute to social capital, which is considered a real factor of organizational success and a competitive advantage. These behaviors therefore improve the productivity and efficiency of organizations by contributing to the achievement of their objectives and the establishment of a serene and beneficial social climate for work (Lievens & Anseel, 2004). Nielsen and his colleagues (2009) have demonstrated that OCB directly influences the performance of employees and therefore implicitly the performance of the organization as a whole. Furthermore, according to Kataria et al. (2013), there is a strong relationship between OCB and organizational efficiency. OCBs are also an effective time-saving tool for managers to be able to channel all efforts on exploiting various opportunities that may arise (Turnipseed & Rassuli, 2005).

Thus, there is evidence of a relationship between OCB and social exchange within organizations (Deckop et al., 1999). According to Zellars et al. (2001), the negative appreciation of employees as well as the disappointments expressed towards them stem from their level of OCB adoption. Bret Becton et al. (2008) proposed that OCB practices could be incorporated as a criterion for employee ratings. It appears that organizations have increasingly begun to adopt this approach.

4- Innovation in organizations

According to Schumpeter (1911), innovation is the fruit of invention resulting from scientific research. For this author, it is a matter of introducing something new into the economic world through marketing. Since this definition, many authors have proposed other visions. For example, Evan & Black (1967) proposed that innovation consists of the introduction of new ideas, products or technologies. Hult et al. (2004) defined it as the ability of the organization to promote new ideas, products and processes. In fact, innovation is a capacity for creativity using a series of procedures, allowing employees to achieve novelties, whether technical, technological or organizational.

The innovation process is articulated around three main phases, namely:

- The ideation phase: at the end of a long brainstorming process, this phase consists of proposing ideas for potential technological or organizational solutions to existing problems. This phase mainly consists of generating, evaluating and selecting ideas (Bergendahl & Magnusson, 2015).
- The invention phase: this phase consists of realizing a new product or process. It includes developing, testing and optimizing prototypes (Fagerberg, 2011).
- The exploitation phase: this phase consists of introducing the invention to the market on the one hand through the ramp-up of production and on the other hand through marketing (Schumpeter, 1942; Dougherty, 1992, Schweisfurth & Herstatt, 2016).

Hagedoorn & Cloudt (2003), on the other hand, divided innovation performance into three phases, namely: invention performance, R&D and patents, and product introduction at the market level.

5- Relationship between OCB and innovation

Previous research in the literature demonstrates the existence of links between organizational citizenship behaviors and innovation. This citizenship is rooted in the social satisfaction of professional relationships as well as the adoption of internal goals (Organ, 1990). According to Katz (1964), the homogeneity of employees' objectives with those of the organization stimulates innovative behavior. This same behavior can be the result of employees' satisfaction through good relationships with their colleagues (Gerke et al., 2015). As a result, if relationships between collaborators generate group satisfaction, innovative behavior will be able to accompany and reinforce organizational goals (Organ, 1990).

Behaviors such as interpersonal help, personal industry, individual initiative and loyalty (Graham, 1989), help to strengthen group cohesion, improve work methods, as well as the sense of belonging among employees. These behaviors also promote innovation by maximizing team effectiveness and efficiency. In addition, OCBs allow organizations to invest in innovation with the goal of addressing potential market failures (Mirabi et al., 2017). Through OCBs, organizational members are bonded by a strong sportsmanship, allowing for a serene work environment characterized by trust, support, and commitment, thus promoting innovation (Mirabi et al., 2017).

As a result, through the very positive impact on innovation, OCB actively contributes to the improvement of the overall performance of the organization. These behaviors also participate

in changing the attitudes of employees, thus enabling innovation in the organization. Employees giving importance to altruism and sportsmanship, for example, would be more apt to promote their organization's innovations towards partners (Mirabi et al., 2017).

Through organizational citizenship behaviors, employees may be able to cope with situations of uncertainty and scarcity of resources, as well as environmental changes and ecological shifts, by equipping themselves with innovation as a major asset (Lindegaard, 2010).

For example, according to Podsakoff and MacKenzie (1997), employees with a good sportsmanship guarantee the organization's ability to adapt to the changes that surround it in its environment, through the motivation to learn new skills and take on new responsibilities in terms of innovation. This sportsmanship therefore contributes to "open innovation", being perfectly compatible with the business model established by the organization (Mirabi et al., 2017). Helping and supporting behaviors, an integral part of organizational citizenship behaviors, are an effective way for collaborators to innovate and adapt with "open innovation" processes. The OCB is also a perfect tool to make the organization's networks work, in order to operate on innovation. Indeed, research has shown that the organization's internal networks are very important for the acquisition of information that allows the optimal achievement of innovation objectives (Hansen & Nohria, 2004).

It appears from all the research we have gathered from the literature review that OCBs have a very important impact on innovation within organizations. We have also noticed through our present article that the model proposed by Organ (1990), containing five key dimensions, namely altruism, civic virtue, benevolence, courtesy and sportsmanship, together with Graham's model (1989) containing loyalty, individual initiative, personal industry and interpersonal help, prove to be the most important and the most adequate with innovation in organizations. Therefore, as a result of our present research, we propose the following model:

Figure 1 : OCB dimensions impact on innovation in organisations.

Source : Authors, Organ (1990), Graham (1989)

Through the model we have proposed, which is mainly based on the theories of Organ (1990) and Graham (1989), it appears that employees will be better invested in terms of involvement and presence and will thus exceed the requirements of the employer. They will also be dedicated to working and collaborating with his team members, which will contribute to the improvement of the work climate and consequently to organizational performance. In addition, they will be involved and dedicated to finding solutions to the organization's deepest problems. As a result, employees will participate in sharing a discourse that positively influences the team's performance internally and the organization's image externally. They will also ensure that their performance exceeds the objectives set by their superiors. These behaviors will significantly reduce the negative attitudes and tensions that may arise between employees and will create a serene climate that will have a positive impact on innovation within the organization.

Conclusion

Innovation is considered a catalyst to promote the reputation and sustainability of organizations. Therefore, in order to enhance innovation, managers are required to increase the OCB of their employees. In this sense, in addition to the collective structural efforts carried out at the institutional level to promote innovation, managers must target the individual level, developing mechanisms for the adoption of OCBs among employees (Mirabi et al., 2017).

Through our present article, our objective has been to identify the relationships between organizational citizenship behaviors and innovation. To do so, we first presented the different definitions of the OCB concept. Then, we identified the major dimensions and antecedents of OCB. Through this part, we focused on the five most important dimensions, namely altruism, benevolence, courtesy, civic virtue and sportsmanship. Then, we focused on the impacts and outputs of citizenship behaviors within organizations. In order to focus on our topic, we also presented the definitions and the main phases of the innovation process. Finally, we have detected the intersections between organizational citizenship behaviors and innovation. At the end of this work, we were able to propose a model linking OCBs and innovation, based on the theoretical models of OCB proposed by Organ in 1990 and Graham in 1989.

One of the main purposes of our paper is to raise awareness among managers about the great importance of deploying and encouraging organizational citizenship behaviors in order to enhance innovation.

It would be relevant in future research to undertake an empirical study in the Moroccan organizations in order to adjust the model we have proposed to that specific context.

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